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Conserving it Together:
Cultural Landscapes—Intangible Heritage

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Traditional cultural events, built heritage and placemaking: The Festival Internacional Cervantino in Guanajuato, Mexico

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Abstract

Traditional festivals are the origin of many international events that have become highly popular over time. This process brings positive outcomes to a city through local pride and an increased number of visitors, but it poses several risks related to overcrowding and loss of authenticity. This research is focused on the Festival Internacional Cervantino, one of the major cultural events in Latin America. The objective was to measure visitors' experiences in relation to placemaking, focusing on the perception of urban services and the city image. The relationship between the festival and visits to heritage sites was especially highlighted and analysed. The methodology that was applied is based on the Event Experience Scale, which is being used worldwide in the study of visitors' event experiences. Findings showed that the Festival Internacional Cervantino only partially contributes to the modification of tourists' perception of the city of Guanajuato. We also found that urban services need improvement and that foreign discourses were incorporated into the festival, impacting fundamental aspects of the city's identity and the event's authenticity.

Introduction

Events play a key role in the contemporary global identity of cities and they also relate to economic, social and cultural processes. Traditional cultural festivities are transformed by contemporary events and the result can be accepted by locals or cause their rejection, thus leading to a loss of authenticity. Events imply a subjective experience for visitors, whose perceptions must be taken into account in order to understand the placemaking itself, given that place relates physical space with social and cultural meaning. The case presented in this research will serve as an example of this relationship and it will contribute to the discussion of the impact of events in placemaking, focusing on tourists' perceptions during the celebration of the Festival Internacional Cervantino in Guanajuato, Mexico.

The main research question in this study was to identify how visitors perceived urban topics in relation to placemaking during the celebration of the event. Changes in heritage site visits patterns were also addressed during festival days. The methodology applied in this research might be applicable to other cities dealing with the same issues.

Traditional events in Latin America responded to a need to break the monotony and offer a reason for citizens to meet, consisting mostly of local people, neighbours from surrounding towns and a few foreigners. However, this purpose has changed in recent decades and celebrating events is now more related to three aspects: attracting tourists, increasing local pride and offering a better city image.

In relation to the capacity of events to attract a larger number of tourists, the focus is especially put on repeat visitors, people making short trips and travelling off-season, and on independent travellers. The main reason to develop events in this sense is that event tourists spend more than average tourists (Herrero et al. 2012).

Regarding local pride, events and festivals are useful for increasing the sense of community and emphasising a positive collective image, especially thanks to the collaborative participation of different kinds of people that share common values and interests, at least for a few days in the year.

Finally, many cities take the opportunity of celebrating events to offer a revitalised city image. Showing a better city image will serve to attract investment and higher-profile residents. This is the reason why there is an increasing number of candidate cities to host events with the highest international impact, such as the Olympic Games or World Expositions. In this case, the value of the event brand becomes more powerful than the brand of the city itself and the impact of the event lasts for decades.

Through the creation and expansion of events, many local traditions have been transformed to attract a larger and more diverse audience. These events serve to transmit local cultural heritage but when the main focus is put on satisfying the visitors' interests rather than local participants' needs, the event can lose authenticity and become less attractive for their original creators (Brida, Disegna & Osti 2013). In these cases, there is a banalisation of intangible heritage and public spaces are turned into spaces of consumption (Paton, Mooney & McKee 2012), thus losing their original objective of being a meeting place during the festival. While events can help to make streets more vibrant (Law 1996), overcrowding by foreign visitors can lead to the displacement of local residents, due to a lack of comfort, and a loss of cultural identity as it becomes a commodified cultural product for tourists. Built heritage does not escape this risk of trivialisation as events are more profitable due to their greater capacity for transformation and adaptation than investment in buildings and monuments (Richards & Palmer 2010). As a result, cities that have focused their tourism strategy on events tourism, might lose interest in conserving built heritage.

The Festival Internacional Cervantino in Guanajuato, Mexico

The city of Guanajuato is the capital of the homonymous state, located in central Mexico, 360 km north of Mexico City, in the region of El Bajío. It is a semi-desert area, in transition between the mild high plateau and the northern deserts, distinguished by their landscape full of cacti and extreme temperatures. The city has 184,239 inhabitants (Instituto Nacional de Geografía y Estadística 2016) and a diverse economy rooted in public administration, university, services, and mining. Although there were previous indigenous vestiges, the city was not founded and permanently settled until 1570 by the Spaniards, following the discovery of a silver deposit, which is still under exploitation. Guanajuato was soon one of the most important silver mines in the Spanish Empire and it became the world's largest silver producer in the 18th century. Guanajuato's city centre and adjacent mines were included in UNESCO's World Heritage List in 1988. Its main values rely on the techniques that were first applied in the city's mines and the rich built heritage that was erected thanks to the economic profit derived from this industry, especially palaces and baroque churches such as the *Basílica Colegiata de Nuestra Señora de Guanajuato*, *La Valenciana*, *La Compañía* and *San Roque*. Apart from mining, the city played a relevant historical role in the Mexican Independence War, represented by the *Alhóndiga de Granaditas* where a decisive battle took place.

Cultural tourism is one of the most important economic sectors in the city. Guanajuato received 2,666,052 visitors in 2017 (8% of them were foreigners) (Secretaría de Turismo de Guanajuato 2018). The main attractions of the city are the monuments that have been mentioned above, the Mummies Museum, and the Festival Internacional Cervantino. This festival is considered the most important cultural event in Latin America. It takes place every year in October and consists of an intense program of visual arts, theatre, music, dance, exhibitions and lectures. In 2017, 186 activities were organised over the festival duration and attended by more than

350,000 people (Unión Guanajuato, 2017). Outdoor activities are free and aimed at a wider audience while those held indoors are focused on new artistic trends and a more specialized audience. The festival is a tribute to Cervantes, one of the most well-known Spanish writers, and his immortal work *El Quixote*. This is a very interesting feature of this festival, taking into account that Cervantes never visited Guanajuato and there is no other connection between the city and the author. However, the city has developed a strong connection with Cervantes since the festival was established, up to the point of being declared America's Cervantes Capital in 2005. Nowadays Cervantes is present in the city all year round in the form of sculptures, street names, plaques and a Quixote Museum.

The origin of the Festival Internacional Cervantino has to be found in Enrique Ruelas' representations of Cervantes' little theatre pieces called *Entremeses* in 1953. In 1972 the festival achieved its current format in general terms (Noticiero del Servicio Exterior Mexicano 2013). Since the 1990s, the festival declined and it started to be popular as a party for young people that wanted to have fun without their parents' control. Lately, new controls have been established on alcohol consumption and antisocial behaviour, although there are tensions between residents and visitors due to noise, waste accumulation and overcrowding. The organisation of the festival is the responsibility of the Federal Government, but many government administrations are involved including the State Government, City Council, and the University. Every year a foreign country and a Mexican state are especially invited, in 2017 it was the turn of France and the State of Mexico.

Figure 1: The street atmosphere in the Festival Internacional Cervantino 2017 (source: the authors).

Methodology

This study's methodology consisted of the application of a questionnaire. The main issues included visitors' perceptions about urban features, heritage visits patterns, and transformations in urban image. The questionnaire is part of a method called Event Experience Scale (EES), which has been developed to measure the experience of people attending events, focusing

Common variables included in EES	Personal information	Place of origin
		Number of people in the group
		Gender
		Age group
		Educational qualification
		Occupational group
		Annual household
	About the visit to the event	Main reasons for attending the event
		Information sources used to plan the visit to the event
		Previous visits to the event
		Accommodation during the event
		Interest in visiting the event again
		Interest in recommending the event
		Importance of the event in the decision to visit the city
		Activities that the person would be doing if the event was not held
		Perceptions and attitudes during the event
		Average spending during the event
		Use of social media to share information about the event
	Specific social media that were used	
	General	Observations
E-mail address		
Specific variables of the study case	About the visit to the event	Location of the accommodation and number of nights that the person stayed during the event
		Events attended
	About the impact of the event in the city's image, attractions, heritage resources and public services and its surroundings	Adjectives that define Guanajuato
		Kinds of transport in the city
		Other activities performed during their stay in the city
		The opinion of event's features and local public and urban services
		Heritage resources visited in the city centre during their stay
		Heritage resources visited in the suburbs during their stay
		Heritage resources and historic cities visited in the surroundings during their stay

Figure 2: Variables that have been used in the questionnaire (source: the authors)

on mood and emotion. The method was designed at Tilburg University in 2012 by Geus, Richards and Toepoel (2015). It resulted in an 18-item scale, comprising 4 dimensions: effective engagement, cognitive engagement, physical engagement, and experiencing newness, with Cronbach's alpha values rating from 0.83 to 0.87. EES has since been applied by members of the Association for Tourism and Leisure Education and Research (ATLAS). ATLAS was founded in 1991 to develop international educational initiatives in tourism and leisure. It serves as a forum to promote the exchange of staff and students, transnational research and facilitate career and professional development. It currently has about 175 members in approximately 60 countries worldwide. In 2014, ATLAS established the Event Experience Research Project with the objective of applying EES in different events worldwide, working together with this method makes it possible to share the data and compare visitors' perceptions of the events that are being analysed. Nowadays, the Event Experience Research Project group is composed of 15 members from Brazil, Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, Greece, Italy, Mexico, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, United Kingdom, and the USA. In Mexico, EES has been applied so far to the Festival Internacional Cervantino in Guanajuato and the Guelagueta in Oaxaca.

In this case study, the questionnaire was applied from 11-29 October 2017, over the duration of the 45th Festival Internacional Cervantino. The questionnaire in this case study included two parts, the first was the original EES comprised 22 closed questions and the second consisted of 8 closed questions focusing on perceptions of urban features, patterns of visits to monuments, and the city's perceived image.

Participants were selected while waiting to enter the main festival venues or walking or having a rest in public spaces connecting event locations. 211 people responded in total, 52% women and 48% men. 83% were from Mexico and the rest were from abroad. Mexicans came primarily from the State of Guanajuato, Mexico City, and the State of Mexico. Foreigners were mainly from the USA.

Key Results and Discussion

Overall, the EES results showed that urban factors are some of the key issues that affect visitors' perceptions of the festival and the city. People from abroad value air and water quality, heritage conservation, security, and accommodation positively, while view issues of accessibility, mobility, traffic and parking negatively. People from other Mexican states are more optimistic in relation to heritage conservation, security, and accommodation, while perceiving parking, traffic and noise negatively. Visitors from the State of Guanajuato consider that the most positive aspects are the festival's venues, public transport, and heritage conservation, compared to the negative aspects of noise, traffic and parking.

It is remarkable that all visitors coincide in valuing the good conservation of the city's historical buildings and monuments. This aspect is crucial for the city's economy and image, taking into account that Guanajuato is included in UNESCO's World Heritage List and heritage tourism is the city's most important tourism element. Other results worth discussing are those related to mobility. Local people are the only ones that value public transport positively, this is possibly related to the fact that they are the main users since people coming from other places might find the city's bus system confusing and unattractive. Related to this is the fact that all people value traffic and parking negatively, which might suggest that a priority should be improving walkability at least during festival days and pedestrianisation in order to make people less dependent on cars. Guanajuato is known for its narrow streets and during the Festival Internacional Cervantino, it is particularly difficult to walk due to the massive presence of cars and various obstacles. People from abroad are the only ones that realise the lack of accessibility for people with reduced mobility, also related to mobility issues, and should be improved. Noise has to do with traffic, overcrowding, and certain performances in the open air, and this is something that should be addressed in order to offer a better experience for attendees. These aspects negatively affect the quality of public spaces, as they become spaces of consumption (Paton, Mooney, McKee 2012) during festival days. If the objective is to make streets vibrant (Law 1996) without causing citizens' objections, the issues identified should be taken into account when designing the public policies reinforcement before and during the event.

Figure 3: Visitors' perceptions of urban aspects during festival days, classifying survey respondents by place of origin (source: the authors).

Figure 4: Waste accumulation and traffic cause difficulties in the city's walkability and a bad impression (source: the authors).

The image that the city offers to residents and visitors is another aspect that affects placemaking in depth. Events serve to modify places in different ways, depending on the values that the festival is built on. People from abroad consider that Guanajuato is mostly historical and traditional. Mexicans think that Guanajuato is a colonial, traditional and historic city. Local people consider that the adjectives that better define the city are colonial and historic.

As mentioned above, events generally contribute to developing a positive image of the hosting city among tourists, residents, and potential investors. Although the Festival Internacional Cervantino is an international event with a high diversity of activities that range from traditional arts to avant-garde performances, it does not contribute to change the perception of the city towards that of modernity.

Guanajuato is widely known as a historic and colonial city thanks to its rich built heritage and, although it might be difficult to add a certain diversity to this image, it would be interesting to do so in order to attract new tourist profiles and creative entrepreneurs (Florida 2014). The opening of the Diego Rivera Museum together with other contemporary art facilities and the installation of avant-garde street art have been positive in this sense. This example shows that the capacity to

modify the city's image by an event is very limited, even if as in this case, the event is a well-established international one.

Figure 5: Visitors' perceptions of the city image during festival days, classifying survey respondents by place of origin (source: the authors).

The final research objective was to analyse how the festival affects the patterns of visits to monuments. Cultural tourism is a main feature of Guanajuato and such changes become relevant to assess. The main venues of the Festival Internacional Cervantino are located in Guanajuato's city centre, where many of the buildings and monuments are concentrated that make the city one of the most popular destinations for heritage tourism in Mexico, with the main attractions including the University, Hidalgo Market, and the Basilica, which is Guanajuato's main church. Outside the city centre, tourists have to intentionally decide to visit certain attractions because they are beyond the main festival sector. In that area, the Pipila Statue is the most visited place, followed by the Mummies Museum in the case of foreign and national visitors, and the Valenciana Church by people from Guanajuato. Apart from local attractions, there are a number of tourist destinations near the city, with the city of San Miguel de Allende being the most popular one.

The Festival Internacional Cervantino contributes substantially to increase visits to specific sites in the city centre, especially those that are close to the main festival venues. This fact probably helps to reinforce the perception of Guanajuato as a colonial and historic city. By contrast, heritage assets that are somewhat separate from the main festival venues are relatively unfrequented, such as the Diego Rivera Museum, which is one of the most important arts-related attractions in the city. It is relevant that the Quixote Museum is not particularly popular, taking into account that the Festival Internacional Cervantino was established as a tribute to Cervantes. In this sense, new venues might be integrated around the already consolidated festival area and the Cervantes-related spirit of the festival should be strengthened in order not to lose the event's authenticity.

Apart from the city centre, other sites are less visited, for instance, the Mummies Museum is one of the most advertised tourist places in the city, but its popularity is limited during the celebration of the festival. In addition, the Valenciana Church is one of the most remarkable baroque churches in Mexico but very few people visit it during the Festival Internacional Cervantino. In this sense, special transport and more publicity could be an offer to these attractions. Surrounding historic mining towns are also not visited during festival days, showing that the importance of mining in the city's history and heritage is not explained as it could be. This case is a clear example of the risks that events bring to built heritage (Richards and Palmer 2010). It is very difficult to develop tourist products from mining heritage, thus, the Festival Internacional Cervantino has turned a blind eye and most of the mining-related sites remain unknown and closed to most visitors. Also, the increasing poor connection of the festival with

Cervantes shows a loss of authenticity (Brida, Disegna & Osti 2013) and there is an increasing emphasis on more competitive and commercial program even if some activities are perceived as excessively commercial and unconnected to local culture.

Figure 6: Visits to heritage assets during festival days, classifying survey respondents by place of origin (source: the authors).

Conclusions

Traditional festivities are the basis for newly developed international cultural events and this process has both positive and negative consequences for cultural heritage places. On one hand, these events help improve social cohesion, street vibrancy, tourism attraction and local pride. On the other hand, when tourism and marketing interests become the priority, the event loses authenticity and residents might feel displaced from the event rhetoric. In the case of the Festival Internacional Cervantino in Guanajuato, its original spirit of serving as a tribute to Cervantes and the city's mining identity has faded into the background and have been replaced by more globalised representations. In addition, the festival is intended to contribute by offering an avant-garde image of the city, but this is overshadowed by its rich colonial heritage, which is the focus of most visits during festival days.

Another aspect worth mentioning is the challenge brought by the concentration of a large number of visitors in a very limited space. During festival days the public space becomes commodified, walkability is restricted due to traffic congestion, and problems such as noise and waste accumulation go beyond the residents' and visitors' tolerance. These issues should be faced appropriately in order to maintain a good quality of urban services and a positive image of the event.

Finally, the application of the Event Experience Scale has proved useful in measuring the experience of visitors attending the Festival Internacional Cervantino. It is a tool that could be applied to other traditional events that receive international attention in different cultural and geographical contexts.

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